

POLITICAL SCIENCES

INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK FOR IMPLEMENTING PUBLIC POLICIES IN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION IN ROMANIA

Apostol Vasile

*Faculty of Management,
Bucharest University of Economic Studies,
Postdoctoral Studies*

Abstract

The development of society is inextricably linked with the course of action in response to the public problems of the real world adopted by each government through public policy.

One of the difficulties faced by Romanian authors is finding terms equivalent to those used in English to adequately translate the terms “politics/policy”.

Public policy is not reduced to a single point act considered in isolated form. Behind each activity, there is a general framework in which the activity is integrated. Although the framework is not explicitly and clearly defined, such as by law or political discourses on government programs, links between activities can be identified.

Public policies are defined by their responsibility or by members of society whose interests are affected by provisions and acts.

Keywords: public policy, administration, politics, society, authority

The institutional framework for the implementation of public policies in public administration includes all institutions, processes, and mechanisms involved in transforming public policies into concrete actions, as well as the monitoring and evaluation of these actions (Marius Constantin Profiroiu, Elena Iorga, 2009, pp. 109 – 124).

In general, this framework can be divided into four components:

Legislative component - this is the legal component that establishes the rights and obligations of public authorities, as well as their role and functions in the implementation of public policies. This includes the constitution, laws, and regulations governing the decision-making and implementation process.

Executive component - this refers to government institutions and administrative agencies that are responsible for implementing public policies. This includes ministries, government agencies, regulatory institutions, and other similar organizations.

Monitoring and evaluation component - this involves the development and implementation of mechanisms for monitoring and evaluating public policies, to verify that they are implemented effectively, and that the objectives set are met. This includes monitoring the performance of government institutions and development projects, as well as assessing the impact of public policies.

Public participation component - this involves the involvement of citizens, non-governmental organizations, and other stakeholders in the decision-making and implementation process. This includes public consultations, public hearings, and other mechanisms to involve citizens in the decision-making process.

Overall, the institutional framework for implementing public policies in public administration must be efficient, transparent, and accountable, to ensure an efficient implementation process and good governance.

Institutional frameworks for the implementation of public policies in public administration differ from country to country depending on their political system, history, and culture.

However, there are some common features that are present in many systems.

In general, most countries have a system of government based on the separation of powers in terms of executive, legislative and judicial power.

The executive is responsible for implementing public policies and is led by a president, a prime minister, or another elected leader.

The legislature is responsible for adopting the laws and consists of a single room or a lower and upper room.

The court is responsible for law enforcement and is independent of the other two branches.

In many countries around the world, there are specialized government agencies that are responsible for implementing policies in a particular field.

For example, there are government agencies for education, health, the environment, and transport. These agencies have some autonomy in decision-making and policy implementation but are subject to government supervision and control.

Public participation is an important aspect of the institutional framework for the implementation of public policies in many countries.

This may include public consultations, public hearings, petitions, and other forms of citizen involvement in the decision-making process.

Regarding the monitoring and evaluation of public policies, many countries have developed specialized agencies that are responsible for collecting and analyzing data on policy implementation and reporting results to the government and the public. These agencies may be independent or may be subordinated to the government (Adrian Miroiu, 2001, pp. 166 – 181).

In conclusion, institutional frameworks for the implementation of public policies vary from country to country, but most include elements such as the separation of powers, specialized agencies, public participation, and monitoring and evaluation of public policies.

The institutional frameworks for the implementation of public policies in European public administration are influenced by the history, culture, and political systems of European countries.

However, there are some common features that are present in most European systems.

Most European countries have a system of governance based on the separation of powers in terms of executive, legislative and judicial power.

The executive is responsible for implementing public policies and is led by a president, a prime minister, or another elected leader.

The legislature is responsible for adopting the laws and consists of a single room or a lower and upper room.

The court is responsible for law enforcement and is independent of the other two branches.

In many European countries, there are specialized government agencies that are responsible for implementing policies in a particular field.

These agencies have some autonomy in decision-making and policy implementation but are subject to government supervision and control.

As in most of the world's states and in Europe, public participation is an important aspect of the institutional framework for the implementation of public policies in many European countries. This may include public consultations, public hearings, petitions and other forms of citizen involvement in the decision-making process.

Regarding the monitoring and evaluation of public policies, many European countries have developed specialized agencies that are responsible for collecting and analyzing data on policy implementation and for reporting results to the government and the public. These agencies may be independent or subordinate to the government.

The European Union (EU) also has an important role to play in implementing public policies in Europe, through its institutions and its policies and programs (Simion Roşca, 2017, pp. 63 – 69).

The European Union has its own institutional framework for the implementation of public policies, which includes institutions such as the European Commission, the European Parliament, and the European Council.

Overall, the institutional frameworks for the implementation of public policies in Europe are characterized by the separation of powers, specialized agencies, public participation, and monitoring and evaluation of public policies, but they can vary from country to country depending on their political and cultural system.

The European Commission is helping EU Member States to improve their public administration and governance system by providing technical support.

This support is provided in the European Union through the Structural Reform Support Programme (SRSP), which aims to strengthen the administrative

and institutional capacity of Member States and other partner countries.

The European Union Structural Reform Support Programme (SRSP) is a European Commission program that provides technical support for EU Member States and other partner countries to improve their administrative and institutional capacity.

The aim of the program is to help countries improve their governance and public administration, strengthen the financial sector, to support the business environment and competitiveness, and promote social development and employment.

SRSP focuses on four main areas:

- 1) governance and public administration reform;
- 2) financial sector;
- 3) business environment and competitiveness and
- 4) social and employment.

For each of these areas, the European Commission and the Member States are working together to identify specific issues and opportunities and to develop an appropriate action plan.

Technical support may consist of providing expertise and advice, organizing seminars and workshops, as well as providing funding and assistance for the development of pilot projects and good practices.

The SRSP program covers a wide range of areas, including governance and public administration reform, financial management, fiscal policy, social affairs, employment, and innovation.

SRSP provides expertise, advice, funding, and technical assistance to help Member States develop and implement public policies in these areas.

SRSP is based on a collaborative approach and involves the expertise and resources of the European Commission and the Member States.

The program encourages the exchange of good practices and experiences between participating countries, and the expertise and experience gained are used to improve existing policies and programs.

Another important objective of the SRSP program is to support Member States and other partner countries in implementing the structural reforms needed to join the European Union and align with policies and EU standards.

SRSP is therefore an important way for the EU to help Member States prepare for EU membership or improve their performance in meeting EU standards.

The European Commission is also working with Member States to promote transparent, accountable, and efficient public administration, through the Technical Assistance and Information Exchange (TAIEX) instrument and through the European Institute of Public Administration (EIPA).

TAIEX provides technical assistance through experts from other Member States, and EIPA provides training and professional development programs for civil servants across Europe.

Digital public administration refers to the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) to improve the efficiency, transparency, and accessibility of public services and the decision-making process in public administration.

This includes the use of the Internet, electronic communications, and automation technologies to provide government services more efficiently and to facilitate communication and collaboration between citizens, non-governmental organizations, and public authorities.

Digital public administration has a number of advantages, including reducing bureaucracy and costs, increasing efficiency and transparency, improving the accessibility and quality of public services, and increasing citizens' participation in decision-making.

Through digital public administration, citizens can access government services at any time and from anywhere, through mobile devices or computers.

Examples of government services that can be offered through digital public administration include paying taxes and fees online, obtaining certificates and official documents via the Internet, registration of companies and completion of other online administrative formalities.

E-government leads to efficiency optimization and facilitates ease of use and accessibility of public services.

Through e-government, government services are provided more efficiently and in a more convenient way for citizens and businesses, without the need for physical travel to government institutions.

The use of digital technologies reduces bureaucracy and simplifies administrative processes, which saves time and money for citizens and authorities.

For example, government services can be offered online, and citizens can pay taxes and fees, request documents and certifications, submit petitions, and do many other activities without having to travel to government institutions.

In addition, e-government optimizes transparency and accountability in public administration by providing more easily accessible information and by involving citizens in decision-making.

Through online platforms, citizens can provide feedback and suggestions on public policies and monitor the work of government authorities.

E-government also improves the accessibility of public services for people with disabilities and other vulnerable groups by providing online services and ensuring an easy-to-use and user-friendly interface.

However, there are also challenges to the implementation of digital public administration, including cyber security issues, limited access to technology, and the need to ensure that all citizens can access government services, regardless of their level of digital competence.

In conclusion, digital public administration is an effective and efficient way for public authorities to provide better public services and involve citizens more in decision-making.

However, it is important to address the issues associated with the implementation of this model and to ensure that all citizens have equal access to digital public services. Another important issue to consider is the need to consider issues related to cyber security and the protection of the personal data of cyber security citizens.

In Romania, the process of modernization regarding public policies and their analysis took place over a long period of time and was difficult (Mariana Nae, 2015, pp. 19 – 22).

The effectiveness and efficiency of public services have been called into question due to the non-corresponding responses caused by several factors such as lack of forecasts, non-definition of objectives, small number of options, poor implementation, and lack of monitoring and evaluation of public policies.

The very definition and diagnosis of the problems specified above proved to be difficult in the conditions of permanent changes and the absence of qualified staff.

It was only at the end of the decade that conceptual methods and frameworks were outdated and inefficient for modern society, which led to an intensification of interest in public policies.

New management theories reformed the public sector after the 90s, and administrative procedures and structures underwent changes due to the fact that the aim was to increase the quality of life.

Managerial reforms required a new style of thinking and behavior since an effective public policy was the determining factor for economic progress and social development.

In general, Romanian public policies have been characterized in recent years by significant changes and reforms, to bring more efficiency and transparency into the decision-making and implementation of public policies.

However, there are still some challenges and issues that need to be addressed, such as corruption, excessive bureaucracy, and social and economic inequities.

Regarding specific public policies, there are certain areas where significant progress has been made, such as public health and education policies, which have benefited from significant investments in recent years.

Public environmental and sustainable development policy has also been the subject of growing concerns in recent years due to climate change and pollution problems.

However, there are also problems in certain areas, such as infrastructure, transport, and regional development, which require significant investment and better coordination between different levels of government.

In addition, there are still significant problems with corruption and economic and social inequities, which adversely affect the efficiency and credibility of public policies.

In Romania, e-government has become a priority in recent years, and the government has implemented several projects and measures to improve public services with information and communication technologies.

Examples of government services that can be offered through e-government in Romania include the payment of taxes and duties online, the submission of tax returns, obtaining certificates and official documents via the Internet, recording, and managing online

business, and accessing medical and educational services through digital platforms.

To support the development of e-government in Romania, the Government has created a series of digital platforms and services, such as the national public service portal “e-Guvernare.ro” and the business portal “Guvern24.ro”, which offers companies quick access to information about the Romanian business environment and a wide range of online services.

In addition, the Government has created The Agency for Romania's Digital Agenda (AADR) which aims to develop e-government strategies and policies and promote the use of digital technologies in public administration.

The Agency for Romania's Digital Agenda collaborates with other government agencies and with the private sector to develop digital solutions and improve public services using information and communication technologies.

Authority for the Digitization of Romania (ADR) is a government institution created in 2018, having as mission the development and implementation of national strategies and policies for the digitization of Romania.

The Authority for the Digitization of Romania is directly subordinated to the Prime Minister and is responsible for coordinating, implementing, and monitoring digitalization and transformation programs in all government sectors.

The Authority for the Digitization of Romania collaborates with public authorities, private sector companies, and other organizations to develop and implement digital solutions so that public services and administrative processes can be improved, and the economy can be strengthened through innovation and technology.

The main objectives of the Authority for the Digitization of Romania are:

- development and implementation of national strategies and policies for the digitization of Romania.
- coordination, monitoring, and evaluation of digital transformation programs and projects within public institutions and the private sector.
- development and implementation of digital solutions for efficient and easily accessible public services to citizens and companies.
- ensuring cyber security and protection of the personal data of citizens and companies.

The Authority for the Digitization of Romania collaborates with other government agencies, including The Ministry of Communications and Information Society (MCSI) and The National Authority for Communications Administration and Regulation (NACAR), to develop projects and initiatives to accelerate the digitization process in Romania.

The Authority for the Digitization of Romania has an important role in promoting and developing digital transformation in Romania.

Through national digitization strategies and policies, the Authority for the Digitization of Romania can help improve the efficiency and effectiveness of public services and can promote innovation and competitiveness in the Romanian economy.

However, there are still challenges in implementing e-government in Romania, including cyber security issues, limited access to technology, and the need to ensure that all citizens can access digital public services.

In addition, there are infrastructure issues, including internet connectivity and access to computers and mobile devices.

E-government can be a powerful tool for improving public services in Romania, but it is important to address the issues associated with the implementation of this model and to ensure that all citizens have equal access to digital public services.

In conclusion, there is significant progress in public policies in Romania, but there are still many challenges and issues that need to be addressed.

It is important for public authorities to continue to implement effective public policies and to address issues and challenges with transparency and accountability.

References

1. Anderson James (1994). “Public policy making” (2nd ed.). Princeton. NJ, Houghton Mifflin.
2. Bondar Florin (2007). “Public policy and public administration”. Polirom Publishing, Bucharest.
3. Ciubotaru Michael Bogdan (2013). “Organization and functioning of the Romanian government. Legislation, doctrine and political practice”. Lumen Publishing House, Iasi. Charles O. Jones (1984). “An Introduction to the Study of Public Policy”. Hachette Brace College Publishers, New York.
4. Colebatch Hal K. (2002). “Policy” (2nd edn). Open University Press, Buckingham.
5. Colebatch Hal K., Hoppe Robert & Noordegraaf Mirko (2010). “Working for Policy”. Amsterdam University Press, Amsterdam.
6. De Leon Peter (1987). „Policy Termination as a Political Phenomenon“. în Palumbo, D. (ed.), *The Politics of Program Evaluation*, Sage, Newbury Park.
7. De Laubadere Andre, Venezia Jean-Claude, Gaudemet Yves, (1999). “Traite de droit administratif”. vol. I, 9e Edition, Paris, 1994.
8. Dye Thomas (1992). “Understanding Public Policy” (7th ed.). Englewood Cliffs. NJ. Prentice Hall.
9. Easton David (1953). „The Political System: An Inquiry into the State of Political Science”. Alfred A. Knopf, New York.
10. Hecl Hugh (1972). „Review Article: Policy Analysis - British Journal of Political Science”. Vol. 2. issue 1, 83-108. Available at: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/british-journal-of-political-science/article/abs/review-article-policy-analysis/134F41132323AA694EE8436AD4D5B915>.
11. Hofferbert Richard.I. (1990). “The reach and grasp of policy analysis. Comparative views of craft”. Tuscaloosa. The University of Alabama Press.
12. Ioan Alexandru (2001). „Administration Theory”. Economic Publishing House, Bucharest.
13. Jay M. Shafritz (1988). “Dictionary of American Government and Politics”. The Dorsey Press-Chicago, Illinois.

14. Jody Zall Kusek, Ray C. Rist (2004). "Ten Steps to a Results-Based Monitoring and Evaluation System". The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development / The World Bank 1818 H Street, NW Washington, DC 20433.
15. Krastev Ivan (2004). *Journal of Democracy* Volume 15, Number 2 April 2004. Disponibil la: <https://www.journalofdemocracy.org/wp-content/uploads/2012/04/Krastev-15-2.pdf>.
16. Lowi Theodore (1964). "Public Policy, Case Studies and Political Theory, World Politics" American Business.
17. Matei Lucica (2001). „Public Management”. Economic Publishing House, Bucharest.
18. Meny Yves, Thoening Jean - Claude (1989). "Politiques publique". Press Universitaires de France, Paris.
19. Miroiu Adrian (2001). "Introduction to public policy analysis". Point Publishing House, Bucharest.
20. Nae Mariana, 2015. „Public policies in territorial development". University Publishing House, ISBN 978-606-28-0370-4, Bucharest.
21. Peters Guy (2021). "American Public Policy - Promise and Performance". Twelfth Edition. USA. University of Pittsburgh. Disponibil la: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/00953997211053501>.
22. Pohoată Gabriela (2017). "Public policy. Theory and practice". Pro Universitaria Publishing House, Bucharest.
23. Popescu Luminița Gabriela (2005). "Public policies". Economic Publishing House, Bucharest. Popescu Luminița Gabriela. "Sectorial Public Policies". SNSPA, Course Support. Bucharest.
24. Profiroiu Marius (2006). „Public Policy - Theory, analysis, practice". Economic Publishing House, Bucharest.
25. Radin Beryl A. (1996). „The Evolution of the Policy Analysis Field: From Conversation to Conversations", 18th Annual Research Conference. Association for Public Policy Analysis and Management. Pittsburgh.
26. Rinfret Sara, Scheberie Denise, Pautz Michelle (2018). „Chapter 2: The Policy Process and Policy Theories". *Public Policy: A Concise Introduction*. SAGE Publications. pp. 19–44. ISBN 978-1-5063-2971-0.
27. Roșca Simion, (2017). „European social model: theoretical approach – practice". Collection of selective articles of the International Scientific Conference „Competitiveness and Innovation in the Knowledge Economy", Vol. IV, E-ISBN 978-9975-75-899-4, Chisinau.
28. Salisbury Robert H. (1968). "The analysis of public policy : a search for theories and roles". Published in: *Political science and public policy*. - Chicago: Markham. Disponibil la <https://www.econbiz.de/Search/Results?lookfor=person%3A%22Salisbury%2C+Robert+H.%22&type=All>.
29. Stone Deborah (2002). „Policy Paradox: The Art of Political Decision Making", Revised Edition. Disponibil la: <https://www.cide.edu/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/Stone-Deborah-POLICY-PARADOX.pdf>.
30. Thoening Jean Claude (1987). "Les politiques publiques", Vol IV, P. XIII, in Madeleine Grawitz. Presses Universitaires de France, Paris.
31. Vida Ioan (2012). "Executive power and public administration". Editura Cordial Lex, Cluj Napoca.
32. Weimer David, Vinning Aidan (1992). „Policy analysis. Concepts and Practice", Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey.